

paper Chain

Baseline Report: PPI waste streams
valorisation potential

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New Market Niches For the Pulp and Paper Industry Waste based on Circular Economy Approaches

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0 Summary

The valorisation potential of waste streams have been screened in five different pulp and paper industries in Europe. The result shows that every single contributor has to at least some extent already some valorisation today of a waste stream, and it also shows that there is a potential to expand the waste stream valorisation.

In this industrial sector the relative size of the waste stream to the main process can be quite small, but on annual basis most waste streams still are in the range of 1 000-50 000 tonnes.

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PPI Waste streams	Waste stream quantification	European PPI	Valorisation potential
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1 Introduction

The purpose of this deliverable is to achieve a quantitative and qualitative analysis of the waste streams from the involved PPI partners (NAV, DOMSJÖ, and VIPAP) and supporting entities (SAICA, Billerud Korsnäs).

These five different industries are all connected to the PPI, but they all have different process characteristics and hence, their waste also differs from each other.

2 Method

The key parameters were identified and questionnaires were made and send out to each contact to fill in. The questions were:

- What is the feedstock of your industry?
- What are your products?
- What are your key process characteristics?
- How do you currently handle your waste streams? What kinds of logistics are involved here?
- What kind of waste stream flows do you have?
- What quantities do you have of your different waste stream flows (on a yearly basis)?
- Do you have any current valorisation options? If yes, please specify.
- Do you have facilities for valorisation options (e.g. handling and storage capacity)? Please specify. Also indicate if this is of interest for you

The answers were analysed on equal premises and the result was compiled into this report.

3 Results

The resulting data from the industrial partners and supporters are listed below in table 1-5.

TABLE 1. DATA FROM DOMSJÖ

	<i>Domsjö Fabriker, Sweden</i>
Feedstock	Wood from spruce and pine
Products	Cellulose (viscose production), lignin and ethanol
Process characteristics	Sodiumbased sulphite mill, bleaching, anaerobic sewage plant
Current waste stream handling	Most of them are valorised or investigated for further valorisation
Type of waste stream and annual quantity	CO ₂ : 17 000 t Biogas: 13 Mm ³ Bioresin: 5 000 t Biosludge: 5 000 t ESP-Ash: 30 000 t Green liquor sludge: 2 000 t Knot residue: 10 000 t Bark: 55 000 t Sawdust: 6 000 t
Current valorisation	CO ₂ is sold for industrial purposes Biogas is used for both internal and external energy production Bioresin is sold as a fuel comparable to fuel oil Biosludge is used as an soil enhancer Knot residue, bark and sawdust are used as fuel
Facilities for potential valorisation	No available facilities today

TABLE 2. DATA FROM NAVIGATOR

	NAVIGATOR Cacia mill, Portugal
Feedstock	<i>Eucalyptus globulus</i> wood
Products	Bleached exucalyptus kraft pulp
Process characteristics	Sulphate mill, bleaching, pulp drying
Current waste stream handling	The mentioned waste below is disposed on landfills adjacent to the mill
Type of waste stream and annual quantity	Grits and dregs 4 500 t Lime mud is unknown due to recent upgrades in the process
Current valorisation	Currently no valorisation of the mentioned waste streams.
Facilities for potential valorisation	The waste is washed and then transported to the landfills without any interim storage. For valorisation facilities for further processing and storage will be needed.

TABLE 3. DATA FROM VIPAP

	VIPAP, Slovenia
Feedstock	The raw materials are recovered paper, spruce and poplar wood
Products	Newsprint, coated/uncoated graphic papers and wrapping/packaging papers
Process characteristics	Integrated papermill with two fibre production plants: DIP-recycled fibre deinked pulp and TGW-Thermal stone groundwood (mechanical pulp). Three papermachines. Three boilers (127,75 MW), wastewater treatment plant, process water preparation.
Current waste stream handling	Waste streams suitable as fuel are used for energy recovery, other streams are handed over to authorized contractors/collectors which either incinerate the waste or send it to landfilling.
Type of waste stream and annual quantity	Bark and wood residues 20 000 t Sludge containing fibres, fillers and coatings 63 000 t Fly ash from boiler 5 200 t Slag, ash, boiler dust 24 000 t DIP-rejects 4 000 t
Current valorisation	Fly ash, slag, ash and dust from boilers are processed into construction products. DIP rejects are processed into cover material and alternative fuels
Facilities for potential valorisation	For the time being the storage capacities are limited; these waste materials generated in the mill are handled and processed on the location where they are built in (e.g. degraded areas). There is interest in being able to handle that matter more effectively.

TABLE 4. DATA FROM BILLERUD KORSNÄS

	<i>BILLERUDKORSNÄS-Karlsborg, Sweden</i>
Feedstock	Wood from spruce and pine, 85% logs and 15% sawmill chips
Products	Kraft paper, bleached sack paper, market pulp
Process characteristics	Sulphate mill with integrated paper mill, bleaching, pulp drying, tall oil and turpentine production, lime
Current waste stream handling	Landfilling, constructional filling material, incineration, composting, material for agriculture
Type of waste stream and annual quantity	Lime: 8 000 t Green liquor sludge: 10 000 t Barksludge: 4 000 t Fly ash: 1 500 t Bottom ash: 2 000 t Methanol: 2500 m3 (1250 m3 oe)
Current valorisation	Today lime is used as construction material for road building, treatment of agricultural soil, covering of landfills. However, there is a potential to recycle this waste stream if there would be a central valorisation facility in northern Sweden and then the lime could be send back to the mills. GLS is today send to landfilling but there is a potential to use it to cover old mining sites. Ashes might be useful as a fertilizer in forestry
Facilities for potential valorisation	No available facilities today, limited capacity on landfill

TABLE 5. DATA FROM SAICA

	<i>SAICA-Waste to energy plant, Spain</i>
Feedstock	Recycled cardboard, rejects from own paper mill, sludge from waste water treatment plant
Products	Recycled packaging paper, energy and steam
Process characteristics	Shredding of raw material, elimination of non-accurate materials (nonferrous metals, metallic materials and PVC), drying of water treatment sludge, boiler with steam turbine. Waste plant integrated in paper mill
Current waste stream handling	The rejects and sludge are sent by trucks to a fuel treatment plant and converted into fuel that is used in a fluidized bed boiler which produces steam and electricity. Ashes from the boiler is send to landfill with trucks. Refused materials from fuel treatment plant are sent to landfill or valorisation, depending on characteristics.
Type of waste stream and annual quantity	Ashes: 58195 tn Ferrous metals: 6000 tn Nonferrous metals: 3000 tn PVC: 9000 tn
Current valorisation	Ferrous metals are sold to valorisation purposes, nonferrous metals are reused. Ashes are being investigated as a binder product
Facilities for potential valorisation	Fuel treatment plant located in El Burgo de Ebro, where around 279000 tn of paper rejects are being handled every year. There is also a sludge treatment plant in the facilities that reduces humidity of around 209000 tn of sludge every year. Storage capacity is around 7000m ³ , 50% rejects, 50% sludge. In addition, the ashes generated in the fluidized bed boiler are temporary stored in three silos with a total storage capacity of 2100 m ³ : 1000 m ³ for waste paper fly ash, 450 m ³ for waste paper bottom ash and another 650 m ³ for any of

them.

These silos are part of a dock bay for storage and delivery of the ashes for both, disposal and valorisation operations.

4 Conclusions

Five different industries have been evaluated for the valorisation potential in their waste streams. The following industries are included: two sulfate mills, one sulfite mill, one mechanical pulp mill, two integrated paper mills and one waste to energy plant. They are all connected to the pulp and paper industry but they are different in type of feedstock, processes and products, and hence also have different types and quantities of the waste streams. Domsjö and Billerud is a good example on how two plants with different main processes, but with practically the same feedstock can have a big difference in waste streams. As an example, the sulfite process that Domsjö uses generates more ESP-ash as waste compared to the sulfate process that Billerud uses. In the sulfate process there is also huge amounts of ESP-ash generated in the recovery boiler but this stream is returned to the chemical cycle in the process. Also Billerud and Navigator uses basically the same main type of process, but have different feedstock which then ofcourse also affects the outcome of the waste streams.

By analysing the type of and the annual amounts of waste a summarising table was achieved, table 6. This is an generalisation which purpose is to point out which key processes that produces the largest amount of waste in the PPI sector.

TABLE 6. SCREENING OF THE MOST COMMON PPI WASTE STREAMS

<i>Most common PPI waste stream</i>	<i>Annual amount per mill (tonnes)</i>
Wastes from boilers as ashes and slags	58 000 – 3 500
Bark and wood residues	65 000 – 20 000
Fibre containing sludge	63 000 – 4 000
Green liquor sludge	10 000 – 2 000
Biosludge	5 000

The data in this report is quite diverse and hard to analyse on itself. However it is a good start for a deeper analysis where this data can be used to estimate the european PPI waste stream valorisation potential.

5 References

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